

Beetles (Coleoptera) in the Tarnowskie Góry-Bytom Subterranean System

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ABSTRACT. Beetles (Coleoptera) in the Tarnowskie Góry-Bytom Subterranean System.

This paper describes research into species of beetles (Coleoptera), which was carried out in one of the largest systems of old mine workings in Europe (Podziemia Tarnogórsko-Bytomskie) near Tarnowskie Góry and Bytom. A one-year survey yielded three species of beetles: *Choleva glauca*, *Pterostichus niger* and *Quedius mesomelinus*. Each species occurred only at particular times of the year, possibly signifying the beginning of the trogllobiont way of life.

KEY WORDS: World Heritage List, Coleoptera, trogllobionts, trogllophiles, *Choleva glauca*, *Pterostichus niger*, *Quedius mesomelinus*.

INTRODUCTION

Underground karst and artificial subterranean systems, e.g. former mine workings, may be “terra incognita” for entomologists. In Poland several thousand caves and cave-like places have been inventoried (KOWALSKI 1956). They differ in their formation and time of origin, microclimatic characteristics, and the lists of species occurring there. Because of the unique microclimatic features of such systems, making them quite distinct from their surroundings, they provide temporary or permanent habitats for unusual species of plants and animals (PARMA & RAJWA 1989). In Poland, detailed studies on cave fauna have been ongoing since the 1950s. However, the fauna of particular karst regions has been explored to quite different degrees (PONIKOWSKI 2008).

The purpose of this study was to determine which species of beetles (Coleoptera) permanently inhabit one of the largest artificial subterranean systems in Europe.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The fieldwork was carried out in the Tarnowskie Góry-Bytom Subterranean System (Podziemie Tarnogórsko-Bytomskie) (UTM CA48). This consists of former workings where silver-, lead- and zinc-bearing ores used to be mined from the 12th to the 20th century. With its over 300 km of corridors and numerous chambers and pits, it is the most extensive subterranean system in Poland (KŁYS 2004), stretching approximately from latitude 50°24' to 50°30' N and from longitude 18°58' to 18°76' E. This area is situated within the physiographic macroregion of the Silesian Upland (Wyżyna Śląska) and

the mesoregion of the Tarnowskie Góry Hump (Garb Tarnogórski) (KONDRACKI 1988). Administratively, it is situated within the boundaries of Tarnowskie Góry, the northern part of Bytom and the western part of Radzionków, all of which are in the Province of Silesia (województwo śląskie). The microclimate of this subterranean system is very similar to that of caves. It is the largest winter hibernaculum of bats in Poland (KLYS 2008). Owing to the vastness of the system, just a 700-metre-long section was chosen for this study; the entrance to it is situated in the vertical face of a quarry next to the Segiet nature reserve (KLYS 2004).

The study was conducted from January to December 2001. Barber pitfall traps, deployed from 10 m to 700 m (at 100 m intervals on average) from the entrance to the system, were used for the live capture of beetles. The average operation time of the traps was two weeks.

The microclimate of the system's interior was studied (KLYS 2004, CAPUTA & KLYS 2005, KLYS *et al.* 2005).

RESULTS

This survey yielded three species of beetles from three families:

Choleva glauca BRITTEN, 1918 (Leiodidae HATCH, 1929)

Pterostichus niger (SCHALLER, 1783) (Carabidae ERICHSON, 1837)

Quedius mesomelinus (MARSHAM, 1802) (Staphylinidae LATREILLE, 1804)

All the insects were caught in the deeper parts of the system (beyond 50 m from the entrance). The number of live specimens caught is shown in Table 1. Each species occurred only at certain times of the year (Fig. 1).

The presence of these populations was confirmed in subsequent years.

DISCUSSION

Detailed studies on cave fauna have been carried out in Poland since the 1950s. However, the fauna of individual karst regions has been explored to quite different degrees. The most important surveys include research into beetles from the family Leiodidae (SZYMCZAKOWSKI 1957). BARYŁA (2000) summarises knowledge of organisms living in Polish caves. Subterranean aquatic communities have been described, for example, by DUMNICKA (2005) and DUMNICKA *et al.* (2007). Artificial subterranean systems have been explored even less often. SKUBAŁA & KLYS (2002) and KLYS (2004) describe invertebrates found in the Tarnowskie Góry-Bytom Subterranean System. PONIKOWSKI (2008) describes the fauna of gypsum karst: the species found there are common throughout Poland.

Choleva glauca BRITTEN, 1918

This species is most frequently found in the vicinity of water in the burrows of rodents (also moles), often in carrion, the burrows of other mammals or plant matter (SZYMCZAKOWSKI 1959). It has also been found in caves, usually close to their entrances and in their vestibules (PAX 1936, KOWALSKI 1953, SZYMCZAKOWSKI 1961).

Table 1. The number and date of live specimens caught.

Tabela 1. Liczba i data zbioru złowionych żywych osobników.

Species	Date	Number of live caught adult beetles
<i>Choleva glauca</i>	5 March 2001	3
<i>Choleva glauca</i>	17 March 2001	28
<i>Choleva glauca</i>	24 March 2001	13
<i>Choleva glauca</i>	27 April 2001	12
<i>Pterostichus niger</i>	16 August 2001	2
<i>Pterostichus niger</i>	23 August 2001	6
<i>Pterostichus niger</i>	22 September 2001	1
<i>Quedius mesomelinus</i>	27 April 2001	2
<i>Quedius mesomelinus</i>	12 October 2001	1

Fig. 1. Occurrence of particular species in the annual cycle.

Ryc. 1. Występowanie poszczególnych gatunków w cyklu rocznym.

Pterostichus niger (SCHALLER, 1783)

A common forest species (ALEKSANDROWICZ 2008), it is found in almost the whole of Europe; it is reportedly also present in the Caucasus, Asia Minor and Siberia. It lives mainly in deciduous and mixed forests, on soils of various types, provided they are sufficiently humid and not barren. In addition, it is found on the banks and shores of water bodies, shaded by trees or bushes (LEŚNIAK 1987, BURAKOWSKI *et al.* 1974), and in caves (ZAGORODNIUK 2004).

Quedius mesomelinus (MARSHAM, 1802)

A common, probably cosmopolitan, species. It leads a subterranean lifestyle, occurring under decomposing remains of plants in cellars, sheds, barns, as well as in mines, grottoes and cave vestibules, where it is the most frequent cave beetle. Moreover, it is found in mole tunnels and marmot burrows, tree hollows and decomposing fungi (KORGE 1961, KOWALSKI 1965).

There are only three known troglobiont beetle taxa in Poland: *Choleva lederiana gracilentata* SZYMCZAKOWSKI, 1957 – both from the Pod Sokolą Górą Cave; *Catops tristis infernus* SZYMCZAKOWSKI, 1957 – Pod Sokolą Górą Cave; and *Speonomus hydrophilus* (JEANNEL, 1907) – from the Dzwonnica Cave in Towarne Mountains.

The first two taxa are relicts from the last interglacial period (KOWALSKI 1951, SZYMCZAKOWSKI 1957). *Speonomus hydrophilus* is not native to the Polish fauna. In 1982, Skalski brought 50 males and 50 females of this subterranean beetle from the Pyrenees and released them in a cave near Częstochowa (KOWALEWSKI 1988, SKALSKI 1990).

These three species of beetles have adapted to life in the Tarnowskie Góry-Bytom Subterranean System. No specimens were found in the area close to the entrance, so their populations have presumably become isolated from their congeners on the surface. It is worth pondering why these species have entered these former mine workings: it may signify the beginning of the troglobiont way of life. Genetic tests will enable one to determine the degree to which the subterranean populations differ from their initial forms. Research on these particular species should lead to finding the reason why they have colonised subterranean systems. The full range of biotic and abiotic components of this environment may well be decisive. These species also possess many features enabling them to survive in this specific subterranean environment.

REFERENCES

- ALEKSANDROWICZ O. 2008. Biegaczowate (Coleoptera: Carabidae) grądu lasu miejskiego w Olsztynie. *Slupskie Prace Biologiczne* 5: 5–14.
- BARYŁA J. 2000. Organizmy żywe w jaskiniach polskich, In: *Jaskinie* No. 3: pp. 19–24. "Szelerewicz", Kraków.
- BURAKOWSKI B., MROCKOWSKI M., STEFAŃSKA J. 1974. Chrzęszcze Coleoptera, Biegaczowate Carabidae, Part 2. *Katalog Fauny Polski* 23(3): 1–430.
- CAPUTA Z., KLYS G. 2005. Rola stacji terenowej w badaniach podziemnych na przykładzie Podziemi Tarnogórsko-Bytomskich, In: KRZEMIEN K., TREPİŃSKA J., BOKWA A. (Eds.), Rola stacji terenowych w badaniach geograficznych. Instytut Geografii i Gospodarki Przestrzennej Uniwersytetu Jagiellońskiego: 239–250.
- DUMNICKA E. 2005. Stygofauna associated with spring fauna in southern Poland. *Subterranean Biology* 3: 29–36.
- DUMNICKA E., GALAS J., KOPERSKI P. 2007. Benthic invertebrates in karst springs: does substratum or location define communities? *International Review of Hydrobiology* 92: 452–464.
- KLYS G. 2004. Przyroda Podziemi Tarnogórskich. Sorex Pyrzowice: 109 pp.
- KLYS G. 2008. Bats in the Tarnowskie Góry-Bytom mines, In: KLYS G., WOŁOŻYŃ B. W., JAGT –YAZYKOVA E., ANNA KUŚNIEZ A. (Eds.). Impact of environmental conditions on the choice of the hibernaculum by bats. Bytom: 30–45.
- KLYS G., CAPUTA Z., KIERAT W. 2005. Wybrane metody pomiarów kryptoklimatu na przykładzie Podziemi Tarnogórsko-Bytomskich. *Nietoperze* 6(1/2): 5–15.
- KONDRACKI J. 1988. Geografia fizyczna Polski. PWN, Warszawa: 463 pp.
- KORGE H. 1961. Die mit *Quedius mesomelinus* MARSH. Verwandten Arten Europas (Col. Staphylinidae). *Entomologische Blätter für Biologie und Systematik der Käfer* 57: 43–53.
- KOWALEWSKI L. 1988. Parki, rezerваты i pomniki przyrody województwa częstochowskiego. Częstochowa: 216 pp.
- KOWALSKI K. 1951. Jaskinie Polski. Warszawa: 466 pp.
- KOWALSKI K. 1953. Jaskinie Polski, t. 2, Państwowe Muzeum Archeologiczne, Warszawa: 186 pp.
- KOWALSKI K. 1956. Jaskinie Polskie. Wiedza Powszechna, Warszawa: 144 pp.
- KOWALSKI K. 1965. Jaskinie Polskie. Warszawa: 144 pp.
- LEŚNIAK A. 1987. Zoogeographical analysis of the Carabidae (Coleoptera) of Poland. *Fragmenta Faunistica* 30: 297–312.

- PARMA C., RAJWA A. 1978. Turystyczne Jaskinie Tatr. Sport i Turystyka, Warszawa: 126 pp.
- PAX F. 1936. Die Reyersdorfer Tropfsteinhöhle und ihre Tierbevölkerung. *Journal, Mitteilungen über Höhlen- und Karstforschung*: 97–122.
- PONIKOWSKI A. 2008. Chrząszcze jaskiniowe (Coleoptera) z rodziny biegaczowatych (Carabidae) w rezerwacie Skorocice (Niecka Nidziańska). Materiały pokonferencyjne „Społeczno-ekonomiczno-przyrodnicze aspekty zrównoważonego rozwoju”, Lublin, KUL: 1–7.
- SKALSKI A.W. 1990. Successful acclimatization of *Speonomus hydrophilus* in Poland. *Bulletin de la Société de Biospéologie, Moulis* 17: 14.
- SKUBAŁA P., KŁYS G. 2002. Orbitid fauna (Acari: Orbitida) in the mine underground workings, In: IGNATOWICA S. (Ed.). *Postępy polskiej akarologii*: 203–212.
- SZYMCZAKOWSKI W. 1957. Catopidae (Coleoptera) des grottesdansles Sokole Góry pres de Częstochowa. *Acta Zoologica Cracoviensia* 1: 65–115.
- SZYMCZAKOWSKI W. 1959. Verbreitung der Familie Catopidae (Coleoptera) in Polen. *Polskie Pismo Entomologiczne* 29: 271–357.
- SZYMCZAKOWSKI W. 1961. Catopidae. *Klucze do oznaczania owadów Polski* 19(13): 1–70.
- ZAGORODNIUK I. 2004. Cave fauna of Ukraine. *Proceedings of the Theriological School* 6: 248 pp.

STRESZCZENIE

Chrząszcze (Coleoptera) Podziemi Tarnogórsko-Bytomskich

Badania gatunków chrząszczy (Coleoptera), które przeprowadzono w jednym z największych sztucznych podziemnych systemów w Europie (Podziemia Tarnogórsko-Bytomskie). W wyniku rocznych badań stwierdzono 3 gatunki chrząszczy: *Choleva glauca*, *Pterostichus niger*, *Quedius mesomelinus*. Ze względu na brak okazów w strefie przy wejściu należy założyć, że te populacje są odizolowane od pozostałych na powierzchni. Poszczególne gatunki występują tylko w określonych porach roku. Autorzy sugeruje, może to być początek troglobiontycznego trybu życia.

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